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LEGAL PROBLEMS ASSOCIATED WITH SEIZURE OF LAND PLOTS FOR STATE AND MUNICIPAL NEEDS

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Annotation: In this article the legal regulation of the land plots seizure for state and municipal needs is analyzed. The basics of legal regulation of land plots alienation are revealed. Special attention is paid to the identification of current legal problems and gaps in legislation related to the seizure of land plots for state and municipal needs. The importance of determining state and municipal needs in the land plots seizure is highlighted. The interrelation of the grounds for the land plots seizure for state and municipal needs with the subjects of jurisdiction of the Russian Federation, subjects of the Russian Federation and municipalities is determined. Judicial practice related to the land plots seizure for state and municipal needs is also being considered.

Keywords: property, land plot, confiscation, state and municipal needs, legal regulation, alienation

ПРАВОВЫЕ ПРОБЛЕМЫ, СВЯЗАННЫЕ С ИЗЪЯТИЕМ ЗЕМЕЛЬНЫХ УЧАСТКОВ ДЛЯ ГОСУДАРСТВЕННЫХ И МУНИЦИПАЛЬНЫХ НУЖД

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Аннотация: В настоящей статье анализируется правовое регулирование изъятия земельных участков для государственных и муниципальных нужд. Раскрываются основы правового регулирования отчуждения земельных участков. Особое внимание уделено выявлению актуальных правовых проблем и пробелов в законодательстве, связанных с изъятием земельных участков для государственных и муниципальных нужд. Выделяется важность определения государственных и муниципальных нужд при изъятии земельных участков. Определена взаимосвязь оснований изъятия земельных участков для государственных и муниципальных нужд с предметами ведения Российской Федерации, субъектов Российской Федерации и муниципальных образований. А также рассматривается судебная практика, связанная с изъятием земельных участков для государственных и муниципальных нужд.

Ключевые слова: собственность, земельный участок, изъятие, государственные и муниципальные нужды, правовое регулирование, отчуждение

In recent years, issues related to the land plots seizure for state and municipal needs have become increasingly relevant. This phenomenon is explained by the fact that the previous legal regulation of the procedure for the land plots seizure was based on the provisions of the Civil and Land Codes of the Russian Federation (hereinafter referred to as the RF CC), which contained a significant number of gaps in the implementation of this procedure.

For example, the list of grounds for alienation of land plots specified in Article 49 of the RF CC is not exhaustive [10, p.163-166].

At the end of 2014, amendments were made to the RF CC, thanks to which the current legislation in the field of land plots seizure and other real estate objects located on them for state and municipal needs was reformed [1-4].

Violation of at least one of the requirements of the procedure for the land plot seizure for public needs serves as a basis for the refusal of the authorized authority to exercise its right to the land plots seizure. Consideration of such disputes should be conducted in court. At the same time, the issue of the effectiveness of the owners and other persons' rights protection to land plots remains relevant. There are cases when public

authorities violated the established procedure for the land plots seizure, which served as the basis for applying to the court.

So, Z. filed a lawsuit against the administration of the municipality of the Safakulevsky district, the Federal State Institution "Tyumenregionvodkhoz" for compensation for losses caused by the land seizure.

The first instance court refused to satisfy the claim. According to the Court of Appeal, during the consideration of the case by the first instance court, the question of whether the land plot was seized from the plaintiffs was not investigated, in connection with which they could have the right to damages. The Court of Appeal found that such withdrawal was carried out in violation of the procedure established by law [7].

It is important to note that while the owner of the land plot will exercise the rights to protect his legitimate interests, a significant period of time will pass during which he needs to pay for his land use. At first glance, there is a clear violation of the rights of the owners of the actually seized land plots, but judicial practice suggests the opposite - satisfaction of public interests is in the first place [7].

The danger of the actual seizure of a land plot by public authorities is as follows: without an agreement on the land plot seizure between the authorized authority and the owner, this plot will not be able to pass into public ownership.

But the public authority, in our opinion, has an interest in refusing to conclude such an agreement on a voluntary basis, since the owner of the land plot will not be able to restore his actual ownership and use of the plot in its original form, and also will not be able to receive full compensation for his property losses, in other words, the redemption value of the land plot decreases, which infringes on the rights and legitimate interests of the owner.

According to the candidate of Legal Sciences E.Y. Gavrulina and graduate student of the Department of Commercial Law and Fundamentals of Jurisprudence of the Faculty of Law of Lomonosov Moscow State University E.V. Borodkina, the relations arising in connection with the withdrawal should not be considered as relations of equal subjects due to the presence of authority when making a decision [5-11].

Since there is no concept of state and municipal needs in the legislation regulating the issue of alienation of land plots, the position of the Supreme Court of the Russian Federation (hereinafter referred to as the Supreme Court of the Russian Federation) is of great importance for law

enforcement practice [6]. The Supreme Court of the Russian Federation was proposed to consider the existing needs of public legal entities for the state or municipal needs for which the land plots seizure is carried out, the implementation of which is aimed at satisfying public interests, however, the implementation of these goals seems impossible without carrying out the procedure for the seizure of privately owned land plots. These provisions make it possible to assert that the seizure of land plots is impossible if there are goals that are only indirectly aimed at achieving public interests and which are primarily aimed at obtaining benefits not by public legal entities, but by private individuals, i.e. withdrawal can be made only in exceptional cases when the achievement of the interests of society is impossible without interference in private interests [8].

A separate chapter in the Land Code of the Russian Federation is devoted to the procedure for the seizure of land plots for the needs indicated above [2]. This once again confirms the relevance of the issue under consideration.

However, Federal Law No. 44-FZ of April 5, 2013 [3] no longer contains such norms, which, in our opinion, is a gap in the current legislation and negatively affects its implementation.

In the subject of the Russian Federation - the federal city of Sevastopol, the seizure of land plots for state or municipal needs for the placement of objects of regional and local significance is carried out by the authorized executive body of state power implementing state policy in the field of property and land relations – the Department for Property and Land Relations of the city of Sevastopol (hereinafter – the Department) [5].

In practice, it is not always possible to resolve disputes related to the seizure of land plots out of court.

So, as a result of the failure of the parties (the Department for Property and Land Relations of the city of Sevastopol and the Skif Dacha-building cooperative) to reach a settlement agreement, the Department for Property and Land Relations of the city of Sevastopol appealed to the Balaklava District Court of the city of Sevastopol with a statement of claim, in which it asks to invalidate the state act on the ownership of the land with a total area of 800 sq.m, the previously assigned cadastral number of the land plot no. (specified) to recognize the defendant's ownership of the disputed land plot as missing, to reclaim it from the defendant's illegal possession into the property of the federal city of Sevastopol, as well as to exclude information about the boundaries of this land plot from the State Real Estate Cadastre.

The claim is motivated by the fact that on the basis of the order of the Sevastopol City State Administration "On the transfer to the ownership of citizens-members of the Dacha-building cooperative "Skif" of land plots for individual suburban construction, the defendant was transferred to the ownership of the above-mentioned land plot and information was entered into the state cadastre of real estate as previously registered real estate objects. Meanwhile, according to information from the State State Institution "Archive of the City of Sevastopol", the Sevastopol City State Administration did not issue an order "On approving the materials for choosing a land plot and granting consent to the service cooperative "Skif Dacha Construction Cooperative" to develop a land management project at the address: Sevastopol zone of the Southern Coast of Crimea". Thus, the disputed land plot was withdrawn from state ownership, without the adoption of an appropriate decision by the authorized body, without approval of the land management project for the allotment of land plots in accordance with the established procedure, which indicates the absence of a legal basis for the defendant to acquire ownership of the disputed plot [9].

Proceeding from the fact that there is an urgent need to develop a single clear methodology for the seizure of land plots, it seems extremely necessary to distinguish the definitions of "state needs", "municipal needs", "public needs".

The list of grounds for alienation of plots specified in the law is not exhaustive, however, the decision of the Supreme Court of the Russian Federation determined that it is impossible to forcibly withdraw in order to benefit other private entities whose activities only indirectly serve the interests of society [6].

In our opinion, it is necessary to strive to ensure that as few land plots as possible are subject to seizure. Already at the stage of planning infrastructure projects, it is necessary to consider alternative options for the location of facilities. When reserving land, other alternatives should also be considered, since the restriction of rights for the time of reservation may also infringe on the rights of owners and other persons who have rights to such land plots.

Thus, it is not legally defined what exactly is considered state and municipal needs and what is not. In our opinion, the introduction of concepts and definitions, as well as a concretized list of grounds in the regulations governing the alienation of land, may in practice have a positive impact on the implementation of the procedure for the seizure of land. This

is extremely important during the active construction and reconstruction of objects of state and municipal significance.

Bibliography

[1] The Civil Code of the Russian Federation (part one) dated November 30, 1994 No. 51-FZ - [Electronic resource]. – URL: <http://base.garant.ru/10164072/>, (date of access: 03/02/2023).

[2] Land Code of the Russian Federation of October 25, 2001 No. 136-FZ (as amended on August 2, 2019) [Electronic resource]. – URL: <http://base.garant.ru/12124624/>, (date of access: 03/02/2023).

[3] Federal Law "On the contract system in the field of procurement of goods, works, services to meet state and municipal needs" dated April 5, 2013 No. 44-FZ [Electronic resource]. – URL: <http://base.garant.ru/70353464/> (date of access: 03/02/2023).

[4] Federal Law “On Amendments to the Land Code of the Russian Federation and Certain Legislative Acts of the Russian Federation” dated June 23, 2014 No. 171-FZ. [Electronic resource]. – URL: <http://base.garant.ru/70681110/> (date of access: 03/02/2023).

[5] Law of the city of Sevastopol dated July 25, 2014 No. 46-3C “On the peculiarities of regulation of property and land relations in the territory of the city of Sevastopol”. [Electronic resource]. – URL: <http://base.garant.ru/23714122/> (date of access: 03/02/2023).

[6] Ruling of the Supreme Court of the Russian Federation of October 27, 2015 No. 309-KG15-5924 in case No. A07-21632/2013. - [Electronic resource]. – URL: <http://www.garant.ru/products/ipo/prime/doc/71140676/> (date of access: 03/02/2023).

[7] Determination of the Judicial Collegium for Civil Cases of the Supreme Court of the Russian Federation dated March 25, 2014 N 82-KG13-5. - [Electronic resource]. – URL: <https://www.garant.ru/products/ipo/prime/doc/70532824/>. (date of access: 03/02/2023).

[8] Review of the judicial practice of the Supreme Court of the Russian Federation No. 1 (approved by the Presidium of the Supreme Court of the Russian Federation on April 13, 2016). [Electronic resource]. – URL: http://www.consultant.ru/document/cons_doc_LAW_196727/. (date of access: 03/02/2023).

[9] Decision of the Balaklavsky District Court of the city of Sevastopol No. 2-3015/2017 dated December 25, 2017 in case No. 2-3015/2017.

[Electronic resource]. – URL: <https://sudact.ru/regular/doc/wGIHEccrXpJ/>. (date of access: 03/02/2023).

[10] Dibirdeev A.V. The problem of the lack of legislative consolidation of the concept of municipal needs in the legal regulation of the seizure of land / A.V. Dibirdeev // Young scientist. - 2019. No. 12. 163-166 p.

[11] Gavrilina E.Yu., Borodkina E.V. Withdrawal of land plots for public needs: current problems and trends [Electronic resource]. – URL: <http://center-bereg.ru/b201.html>. (date of access: 03/02/2023).

Список литературы (перевод)

[1] Гражданский кодекс Российской Федерации (часть первая) от 30.11.1994 № 51-ФЗ - [Электронный ресурс]. – URL: <http://base.garant.ru/10164072/>, (дата обращения: 02.03.2023).

[2] Земельный кодекс Российской Федерации от 25.10.2001 № 136-ФЗ (ред. от 02.08.2019) [Электронный ресурс]. – URL: <http://base.garant.ru/12124624/>, (дата обращения: 02.03.2023).

[3] Федеральный закон "О контрактной системе в сфере закупок товаров, работ, услуг для обеспечения государственных и муниципальных нужд" от 05.04.2013 № 44-ФЗ [Электронный ресурс]. – URL: <http://base.garant.ru/70353464/> (дата обращения: 02.03.2023).

[4] Федеральный закон «О внесении изменений в Земельный кодекс Российской Федерации и отдельные законодательные акты Российской Федерации» от 23.06.2014 № 171-ФЗ. [Электронный ресурс]. – URL: <http://base.garant.ru/70681110/> (дата обращения: 02.03.2023).

[5] Закон города Севастополя от 25 июля 2014 года № 46-ЗС «Об особенностях регулирования имущественных и земельных отношений на территории города Севастополя». [Электронный ресурс]. – URL: <http://base.garant.ru/23714122/> (дата обращения: 02.03.2023).

[6] Определение Верховного Суда Российской Федерации от 27.10.2015 г. № 309-КГ15-5924 по делу № А07-21632/2013. - [Электронный ресурс]. – URL: <http://www.garant.ru/products/ipo/prime/doc/71140676/> (дата обращения: 02.03.2023).

[7] Определение Судебной коллегии по гражданским делам Верховного Суда РФ от 25 марта 2014 г. N 82-КГ13-5. - [Электронный ресурс]. – URL: <https://www.garant.ru/products/ipo/prime/doc/70532824/>. (дата обращения: 02.03.2023).

[8] Обзор судебной практики Верховного Суда Российской Федерации № 1 (утв. Президиумом Верховного Суда Российской Федерации 13.04.2016). [Электронный ресурс]. – URL: http://www.consultant.ru/document/cons_doc_LAW_196727/. (дата обращения: 02.03.2023).

[9] Решение Балаклавского районного суда города Севастополя № 2-3015/2017 от 25 декабря 2017 г. по делу № 2-3015/2017. [Электронный ресурс]. – URL: <https://sudact.ru/regular/doc/wGIHEccrXpJ/>. (дата обращения: 02.03.2023).

[10] Дибирдеев А.В. Проблема отсутствия законодательного закрепления понятия муниципальных нужд в правовом регулировании изъятия земельных участков / А.В. Дибирдеев // Молодой ученый. – 2019. №12. 163-166 с.

[11] Гаврилина Е.Ю., Бородкина Е.В. Изъятие земельных участков для публичных нужд: актуальные проблемы и тенденции [Электронный ресурс]. – URL: <http://center-bereg.ru/b201.html>. (дата обращения: 02.03.2023).

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